

**Supplementary Material S10:
Additional information of the
statistical analysis**

Analysis of residuals normality and variances homogeneity


```
Residuals F1 Macro:  
p-value = 0.001: Residuals are not normally distributed (reject H0)  
Residuals Accuracy:  
p-value = 0.000: Residuals are not normally distributed (reject H0)  
F1 Macro Levene's Test:  
p-value = 0.000, Variances are not equal (reject H0)  
Accuracy Levene's Test:  
p-value = 0.000, Variances are not equal (reject H0)
```

Comparison between the MLAs and the control algorithm (DUMMY) in FD1

*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.0180368000195199
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	RF	SVM	LDA	NB	MLP	DUMMY
RF	-	NS	NS	NS	NS	*
SVM	NS	-	NS	NS	NS	*
LDA	NS	NS	-	NS	NS	*
NB	NS	NS	NS	-	NS	*
MLP	NS	NS	NS	NS	-	*
DUMMY	*	*	*	*	*	-

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.025297899348512294
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	RF	SVM	LDA	NB	MLP	DUMMY
RF	-	NS	NS	NS	NS	*
SVM	NS	-	NS	NS	NS	*
LDA	NS	NS	-	NS	NS	*
NB	NS	NS	NS	-	NS	*
MLP	NS	NS	NS	NS	-	*
DUMMY	*	*	*	*	*	-

Comparison between the MLAs and the control algorithm (DUMMY) in FD2

A) F1 Macro by Algorithm
B) Accuracy by Algorithm

*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.003350496634237473
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	RF	SVM	LDA	NB	MLP	DUMMY
RF	-	NS	NS	NS	NS	*
SVM	NS	-	NS	NS	NS	*
LDA	NS	NS	-	NS	NS	*
NB	NS	NS	NS	-	NS	*
MLP	NS	NS	NS	NS	-	*
DUMMY	*	*	*	*	*	-

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.001182930851076427
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	RF	SVM	LDA	NB	MLP	DUMMY
RF	-	NS	*	NS	NS	*
SVM	NS	-	NS	NS	NS	*
LDA	*	NS	-	NS	NS	*
NB	NS	NS	NS	-	NS	*
MLP	NS	NS	NS	NS	-	*
DUMMY	*	*	*	*	*	-

Comparison between the MLAs and the control algorithm (DUMMY) in FD3

A) F1 Macro by Algorithm
B) Accuracy by Algorithm

*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
1.552385006530021e-05
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	RF	SVM	LDA	NB	MLP	DUMMY
RF	-	NS	*	NS	NS	**
SVM	NS	-	NS	NS	NS	**
LDA	*	NS	-	NS	NS	**
NB	NS	NS	NS	-	NS	**
MLP	NS	NS	NS	NS	-	**
DUMMY	**	**	**	**	**	-

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
6.702313236272252e-05
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	RF	SVM	LDA	NB	MLP	DUMMY
RF	-	NS	NS	NS	NS	**
SVM	NS	-	NS	NS	NS	**
LDA	NS	NS	-	NS	NS	**
NB	NS	NS	NS	-	NS	**
MLP	NS	NS	NS	NS	-	**
DUMMY	**	**	**	**	**	-

Analysis of MLA and GSA in FD1

A) F1 Macro by GSA:

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
 0.13929870626161536
 Fail to reject the null hypothesis:
 There is no significant difference between the groups.

B) Accuracy by GSA:

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
 0.019228795415171578
 Reject the null hypothesis:
 There is a significant difference between the groups.

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	LASSO	Membrane	Surfaceome
LASSO	-	NS	**
Membrane	NS	-	*
Surfaceome	**	*	-

C) F1 Macro by MLA:

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
 1.0
 Fail to reject the null hypothesis:
 There is no significant difference between the groups.

D) MLA Accuracy by MLA:

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
 1.0
 Fail to reject the null hypothesis:
 There is no significant difference between the groups.

*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

Analysis of MLA and GSA in FD2

A) F1 Macro by GSA:

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):  
1.0  
Fail to reject the null hypothesis:  
There is no significant difference between the groups.
```

B) Accuracy by GSA:

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):  
0.8380631306617315  
Fail to reject the null hypothesis:  
There is no significant difference between the groups.
```

C) F1 Macro by MLA:

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):  
0.4111733235398697  
Fail to reject the null hypothesis:  
There is no significant difference between the groups.
```

D) Accuracy by MLA:

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):  
0.09721170573118681  
Fail to reject the null hypothesis:  
There is no significant difference between the groups.
```


*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

Analysis of MLA and GSA in FD3

A) F1 Macro by GSA:

```

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.0006043289964537235
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:
LASSO Surfaceome Membrane Network analysis FIS
LASSO - NS NS NS NS **
Surfaceome NS - NS NS * **
Membrane NS NS - NS NS
Network analysis NS * NS NS - *
FIS ** ** NS NS * -
    
```

B) Accuracy by GSA:

```

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.0024193257716561773
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:
LASSO Surfaceome Membrane Network analysis FIS
LASSO - NS NS NS NS *
Surfaceome NS - NS NS NS **
Membrane NS NS - NS NS
Network analysis NS NS NS NS - *
FIS * ** NS NS * -
    
```

C) F1 Macro by MLA:

```

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.8496860881292019
Fail to reject the null hypothesis:
There is no significant difference between the groups.
    
```

D) Accuracy by MLA:

```

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.12437663236228734
Fail to reject the null hypothesis:
There is no significant difference between the groups.
    
```

*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

Analysis of Factorial Designs

A) F1 Macro by FD

B) Accuracy by FD

*** Statistically significant**

NS: Not statistically significant

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
2.2414490735941875e-10
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	FD1	FD2	FD3
FD1	-	***	***
FD2	***	-	NS
FD3	***	NS	-

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
2.8750201290308476e-07
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.
```

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:

	FD1	FD2	FD3
FD1	-	***	***
FD2	***	-	**
FD3	***	**	-

Analysis with ET and AdaBoost in FD3

A) F1 Macro by Algorithm
B) Accuracy by Algorithm

*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.07820000603605885
Fail to reject the null hypothesis:
There is no significant difference between the groups.
```

```
Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.003946528558117272
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:
  RF SVM LDA NB MLP ET ADA
RF  -  NS  NS  NS  NS  NS  NS
SVM NS  -  NS  NS  NS  NS  NS
LDA NS  NS  -  NS  NS  NS  NS
NB  NS  NS  NS  -  NS  NS  NS
MLP NS  NS  NS  NS  -  NS  NS
ET  NS  NS  NS  NS  NS  -  NS
ADA NS  NS  NS  NS  NS  NS  -
```

Analysis of Feature Importance Score in FD3

*** Statistically significant**
NS: Not statistically significant

```

Kruskal-Wallis p-value adjusted (Bonferroni):
0.00019663600560468512
Reject the null hypothesis:
There is a significant difference between the groups.

Steel-Dwass Post Hoc Comparisons:
      FIS-AUC  LASSO  Membrane  Network  Surfaceome
FIS-AUC      -      **      **      **      **
LASSO        **      -      NS      NS      NS
Membrane     **      NS      -      NS      NS
Network      **      NS      NS      -      NS
Surfaceome   **      NS      NS      NS      -
    
```